

1 **Vivid Volcano: Empowering Non-Bioinformaticians to** 2 **Analyze Pre-Processed Omics Data**

3 Tomasz M. Stępkowski, PhD*

4 * DatViseR – Independent R developer (<https://github.com/DatViseR>)

5 ORCID: [0000-0002-8454-4421](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8454-4421)

6 **Summary**

7 **Vivid Volcano is an R Shiny web application – an intuitive tool that helps**
8 **experimental scientists with no bioinformatics background explore and analyze pre-**
9 **processed omics data. It enables users to perform crucial bioinformatic analyses**
10 **without the help of specialists. With Vivid Volcano, one can create highly customizable,**
11 **publication-ready volcano plots and perform comprehensive data exploration, and**
12 **gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis. Users can download variously formatted**
13 **publication-ready plots and neatly formatted tables that adhere to scientific standards.**
14 **Vivid Volcano empowers both exploratory and explanatory data analysis.**

15 **Statement of need**

16 Modern biological research relies heavily on omics technologies (genomics,
17 proteomics, transcriptomics, etc.) that generate large, complex datasets requiring
18 specialized analysis and processing by bioinformaticians – experts with a unique
19 combination of programming, statistics, and data science skills blended with biology
20 domain knowledge(Manzoni et al. 2018). These experts build analysis pipelines which
21 produce pre-processed data conveying metadata on experiments and statistical results for
22 the changes in expression of thousands of proteins, genes, etc. However, to draw valid
23 biological conclusions, this pre-processed data must be explored and explained by
24 subdomain experts who are usually experimentalists who designed the experiments. Those
25 often do not have strong computational skills to effectively explore data and visualize crucial

26 conclusions. Despite the widespread adoption of omics technologies in biological research,
27 many experimental scientists struggle with data analysis due to technical barriers and
28 communication challenges between computational and experimental disciplines, even with
29 bioinformatician support.

30 Vivid Volcano was designed with two basic aims:

- 31 1. Empowering experimental biologists with a tool that can help them explore and analyze
32 pre-processed omics data on their own
- 33 2. Lowering the workload for bioinformaticians who can focus on more statistically and
34 computationally challenging tasks such as integration of complex multiomics data

35 Vivid Volcano addresses a critical need in the biological research community by
36 empowering wet-lab scientists to independently analyze and interpret preprocessed omics
37 data without requiring programming expertise or extensive bioinformatics support. The
38 application provides an accessible interface for uploading and diagnosing preprocessed
39 omics data, performing customized statistical analyses including gene set enrichment
40 analysis across more than 8,000 GO categories, and generating publication-ready
41 visualizations. Unlike many existing tools, Vivid Volcano maintains a simple and efficient
42 design that does not rely on Bioconductor libraries, making it more accessible and easier to
43 maintain. Vivid Volcano was designed to provide a smooth and intuitive user experience. For
44 more advanced users who would like to validate the under-the-hood processes, the
45 application also implements a process log system that tracks data processing outcomes,
46 facilitating debugging and enabling analysis of app functionality. These features collectively
47 enable experimental biologists to gain deeper insights from their omics data, accelerate
48 research workflows, and produce publication-quality outputs without advanced
49 computational skills.

50 In summary Vivid Volcano has been designed based on firsthand experience with the
51 challenges faced by experimental biologists working with omics data and aims to provide

52 comprehensive yet accessible solutions for generating publication-ready outputs from
53 preprocessed omics datasets.

54 The application is available online at [https://datviser-vivid-](https://datviser-vivid-volcano.share.connect.posit.cloud/)
55 [volcano.share.connect.posit.cloud/](https://datviser-vivid-volcano.share.connect.posit.cloud/), making it readily accessible to researchers worldwide.

56 The source code is available at <https://github.com/DatViseR/Vivid-Volcano>.

57 Technical description and implementation

58 Vivid Volcano is built as a modular R Shiny web application leveraging the robust
59 reactive programming model that Shiny provides. The application architecture is
60 characterized by clear separation between the user interface, server logic, and data
61 processing components. The core functionality is implemented in R, with CSS for custom
62 styling and JavaScript for enhanced interactivity. The application utilizes several key R
63 packages, among others: shiny for the web framework (Chang et al. 2024) ,
64 shiny.semantic(Stachura et al. 2024) for user interface, DT for interactive data tables(Xie,
65 Cheng, and Tan 2024) , ggplot2(Wickham 2016) and plotly(Sievert 2020) for generating
66 publication-quality visualizations, GT for publication ready tables(lannone et al. 2024) and
67 shinyjs(Attali 2021) and shinyalert(Attali and Edwards 2024) for improved user experience .
68 For statistical analysis, the application employs basic R operations and custom functions
69 for ontology enrichment that don't rely on Bioconductor dependencies, making the
70 application more accessible and maintainable as a web tool. Data processing is handled
71 through dplyr, tidyr, and other tidyverse packages which provide efficient data manipulation
72 capabilities[Wickham et al. (2023)](Wickham, Vaughan, and Girlich 2024) . The application
73 implements a custom logging system to track all data transformations, ensuring
74 transparency and reproducibility of results. Vivid Volcano's modular design allows for
75 straightforward extension and maintenance, with clearly separated UI modules for data
76 upload, visualization, statistical analysis, and results export. The application is deployed on
77 Posit Connect Cloud (formerly RStudio Cloud), making it accessible via web browser without
78 requiring local installation.

79 Statistics and Limitations

80 Vivid Volcano takes an innovative approach to gene set enrichment analysis by
81 prioritizing speed and accessibility without sacrificing essential statistical rigor. Unlike many
82 similar tools, it does not rely on Bioconductor libraries, which makes the application
83 significantly faster, more lightweight, and better suited for web-based deployment and non-
84 technical user. This independence from heavy computational dependencies allows
85 researchers to analyze data quickly in a browser interface, without requiring specialized
86 software installation. Standard Bioconductor packages typically operate on complex data
87 structures and specialized objects that, while powerful for comprehensive analyses,
88 introduce significant computational overhead unsuitable for responsive web applications.
89 Vivid Volcano addresses this limitation by storing crucial Gene Ontology information in
90 highly optimized binary parquet files—a column-oriented data format designed for efficient
91 querying and retrieval. This streamlined approach provides rapid access to approximately
92 8,000 GO categories and their gene associations without the memory and processing
93 demands of traditional Bioconductor implementations. Vivid Volcano’s gene set enrichment
94 analysis is based on the hypergeometric test, a robust method for determining whether
95 specific gene sets are overrepresented among regulated genes. This test calculates the
96 probability of observing the particular overlap between regulated genes and genes belonging
97 to specific GO categories by chance. By comparing the actual number of regulated genes in
98 a category against what would be expected randomly, the test provides a measure of
99 enrichment. The implementation utilizes four key values: the total genes detected in the
100 experiment, the number of genes in a given GO category, the total regulated genes in the
101 experiment, and the number of regulated genes found in that category. To control false
102 positives, Vivid Volcano implements multiple safeguards: multiple testing correction,
103 customizable significance thresholds, fold enrichment filtering, and gene set size limitations
104 that exclude very small or overly broad categories. The application also transparently
105 addresses the limitations of standard p-value adjustment methods when applied to Gene
106 Ontology data. As noted in the footnotes of the results tables, traditional approaches like

107 Benjamini–Hochberg (BH) were not developed specifically for hierarchical data structures
108 like the GO tree. Thus, biologically meaningful “parent” categories might be missed when
109 BH over-corrects due to many related, statistically significant “child” categories.
110 Conversely, overly broad categories can become significant when BH under-corrects, driven
111 primarily by very highly significant specialized subcategories.

112 Instead of implementing complex solutions that might impede performance and
113 confuse users, Vivid Volcano offers a smooth user experience while clearly communicating
114 methodological considerations. The application provides a pragmatic balance between
115 statistical precision and practical utility, making sophisticated analyses accessible to
116 researchers without extensive bioinformatics expertise.

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117 **Figures**

118

119 *Figure 1. Data upload and data select and curation modules of the Vivid Volcano*

120 *application*

The image shows a 'State of data source preview' window with a search bar and a datatable. The datatable has columns for Fold, pvalue, qvalue, Sequence, Proteins, Leading razor protein, Gene names, and Protein names. The data is as follows:

Fold	pvalue	qvalue	Sequence	Proteins	Leading razor protein	Gene names	Protein names
0.128764093	0.527601532	0.47528757	AAESLADPTEYENLFPGLK	P35606:A0A7I2V258;H0Y938;H0YAC7	P35606	COPB2	Coatomer subunit beta
-0.025836267	0.097555613	0.888897025	AASADSTTEGTPADGFTVLSTK	O75367	O75367	H2AFY	Core histone macro-H2A.1
-0.058202565	0.168147368	0.787501926	AASDIAMTELPPTHPIR	P62258;K7EM20	P62258	YWHAE	14-3-3 protein epsilon
0.059923351	0.470498342	0.671513196	AATLILEPAGR	Q86TX2;G3V4F2;A0A2R8Y7H3;A0A087X0W7	Q86TX2	ACOT1;ACOT2	Acyl-coenzyme A thioesterase 1
0.188453883	0.819205711	0.31053951	AATPQVAELEK	O95900	O95900	TRUB2	Probable tRNA pseudouridine synthase 2
-0.225386441	1.750072533	0.151245714	AAVEDSGTTVETIK	Q5VTR2;C9JWJ4;C9J0A5;C9JXC9	Q5VTR2	RNF20	E3 ubiquitin-protein ligase BRE1A
-0.092001975	0.143305155	0.773546527	ACMLTATAHGDVNVISWSR	Q9BQ67;M0QX71	Q9BQ67	GRWD1	Glutamate-rich WD repeat-containing protein 1
-0.149078012	0.196231484	0.680421053	ADIFVDPVLHTACALDIK	Q92896	Q92896	GLG1	Golgi apparatus protein 1
0.133380353	0.320458873	0.590739274	ADLLLSIQPGREGESPLELER	P08195;F5GZIO;F5GZ56;J3KPF3	P08195	SLC3A2	4F2 cell-surface antigen heavy chain
0.126187533	1.681475426	0.301296089	ADMDDQFTASISETPVDVR	Q06481	Q06481	APLP2	Amyloid-like protein 2

At the bottom of the table, there is a pagination control showing 'Previous', '1', '2', '3', '4', '5', '...', '98', and 'Next'.

121

122 *Figure 2. Interactive datatable preview of the analyzed data in the Vivid Volcano application.*

123

124 *Figure 3. Volcano plot customisation options in the Vivid Volcano application*

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126
 127 *Figure 4. Volcano plot and publication ready tabular results generated with Vivid Volcano*
 128 *application*

129
 130 *Figure 5. Preview of the gene list annotations for the detected and regulated genes present*
 131 *within the given GO category in the Vivid Volcano application*

132

133 *Fig.6. The results of Gene Set Enrichment analysis performed with Vivid Volcano*
 134 *application*

135

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142 AI statement

143 The author used Claude Sonnet 3.7 to copy edit and proofread the manuscript. The author
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